

FORENSIC ANALYSIS OF INJURIES TO LARGE JOINTS SUSTAINED IN DOMESTIC TRAUMA

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In forensic practice, damage to large joints is not common. Such damage can be sustained under various circumstances. Forensic assessment of damage to large joints is associated with certain difficulties, primarily due to the complexity of the anatomical structure and the diversity of the mechanism of damage. In specialized literature, various aspects of this problem are not sufficiently covered (V.A. Klevno, N.V. Tarasova, 2017; S.N. Kulikov, 2023).

The aim of the study is to examine the characteristics of damage to large joints resulting from domestic trauma.

Material and methods of research. The materials of forensic medical examinations of living persons conducted in the city of Tashkent in 2021 were analyzed. A total of 350 examinations were conducted regarding damage to large joints, which accounted for 3.3% of mechanical damage. In 20 cases (5.7%), the damage was caused by domestic trauma. The data of medical documents, examination by a forensic expert, as well as the results of instrumental studies and specialist consultations conducted during the examination were studied.

Results of the research and their discussion. According to the forensic medical examination materials, damage to large joints in household trauma was observed equally in men and women, more often at the age of 18-39 years (55%). By time of day, the most frequent injuries were received during the period from 13-18 hours and 19-24 hours (35% each). Of the 20 cases, 5 were associated with falls, mainly from one's own height, and the remaining 15 - with beatings.

All victims sought medical care, of which 70% were limited to outpatient treatment. In household injuries, the injuries were often isolated (75%), in particular, there were injuries to the shoulder and knee joints (25% each). In 5 cases, the injury was combined, of which in two cases (10%) there were injuries to two joints of the upper limbs, in three cases (15%) - to two or more joints of both limbs.

According to the morphological characteristics, in household trauma the following were mainly observed: fractures with contusion and rupture of

periarticular tissues (35%), contusions, ruptures of periarticular soft tissues (25%), dislocations and hemarthrosis with contusion or rupture of soft tissues (15% each). Other types of joint injuries were much less common.

In determining the severity of injuries, the most frequently used criterion was the duration of the health disorder (65%). In other cases, the severity was determined by the degree of persistent loss of general working capacity. According to the severity of injuries, they were classified as moderate (30%) and minor physical injuries that resulted in a health disorder (20%). In 3 cases (15%), the injuries did not result in a short-term health disorder or minor persistent loss of working capacity. In 7 cases (35%), joint trauma was combined with damage to the brain and internal organs and, according to the criterion of danger to life, it was classified as a serious injury.

Conclusion

1. Damage to large joints due to domestic trauma was observed equally in men and women, more often in people aged 18-49 years, in the second half of the day and was associated with beatings.

Isolated injuries to the shoulder and knee joints and injuries in the form of fractures with contusions and ruptures of periarticular tissues, contusions, ruptures of periarticular soft tissues occurred more frequently. In most cases, the severity of the injuries was determined by the criterion of the duration of the health disorder.

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